

Research on Performance Evaluation of Third-Party Institutions Participation in Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services

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Abstract

China has rapidly entered an aging society. Government purchase of elderly care service becomes a feasible way to improve the level of elderly care service. This study comprehensively investigated and analyzed purchasing elderly care services and third-party performance evaluation of purchasing elderly care services in Jiangsu province, China from 2018 to 2020. On the basis of current situation analysis, this paper constructed the performance evaluation mechanism of the third party for purchasing elderly care service. Countermeasures and suggestions are proposed from the perspective of government purchaser, elderly care services undertaking and third party institution.

Keywords: Purchase Elderly Care Services, Third Party, Performance Evaluation

1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

China has rapidly entered an aging society. It took decades or even hundreds of years for western developed countries to achieve aging, but only 20 years (1981-2021) for China. In the context of the rapid increase in the total demand for elderly care services in China, the continuous improvement of service quality requirements and the limited financial resources, the contradiction between the traditional government supply mode and the increasing demand for the quantity and quality of pension service is becoming more and more prominent. Government purchase of pension service becomes a feasible way to improve the level of pension service. To ensure the effective implementation of government purchase of elderly care services, "establishing and improving the supervision mechanism" is the key. The third-party evaluation is independent, objective, professional, fair, and just. Therefore, the performance evaluation of the third party's high-quality participation in the government's purchase of elderly care services has become an urgent problem to be solved.

In 2018, the Ministry of Finance of the People's Republic of China required that the government purchasing public services for the benefit of the public should actively introduce third-party institutions to carry out performance evaluation, and evaluate the economy, standardization, efficiency and fairness of the purchase of services. On August 14, 2018, the Ministry of Finance of The People's Republic of China issued guiding Opinions on Promoting third-party performance Evaluation of Government Purchase Services.^[1] The guideline calls for solid and orderly progress in third-party performance evaluation of government purchase of services, continuous improvement of standardized and institutionalized management, gradual expansion of the coverage of performance evaluation projects, and efforts to improve the efficiency of government funds and the management of government public services. It follows the principles of openness, fairness, and justice, encourages competition based on merit, pays attention to standardized operation, gives full play to the professional advantages of third-party evaluation institutions, and ensures objective, fair, and credible evaluation results. The purchaser is responsible for the specific organization work of performance evaluation carried out by third-party institutions; Third-party institutions shall carry out performance

evaluation in accordance with laws and regulations and be responsible for the authenticity of the evaluation results; The undertaking subject shall cooperate in carrying out performance evaluation.

On March 29, 2019, The General Office of the State Council of the People's Republic of China issued No. 5 of the Opinions on Promoting the Development of Elderly Care Services, which clearly required the improvement of the precision level of government input. ^[2] The Ministry of Civil Affairs and local governments at all levels will allocate no less than 55 percent of their lottery funds for social welfare programs to support the development of old-age services by 2022. Old-age care institutions that receive elderly disabled persons with economic difficulties shall enjoy operation subsidies equally according to the number of the above-mentioned elderly persons regardless of the nature of the operation, and the above-mentioned elderly persons shall enjoy old-age service subsidies according to regulations. The elderly care service will be included in the guideline list for government procurement of services, a comprehensive review of the various elderly care services currently arranged by government expenditures, and provincial-level standards for government procurement of elderly care services, with a focus on purchasing services such as living care, rehabilitation care, institution operation, social work and personnel training. On December 23, 2019, the People's Government of Jiangsu Province also issued the "Implementation Opinions on Further Promoting the High-quality Development of Elderly Care Services" su Zhengfa (2019) No. 85. ^[3] We will actively promote the high-quality development of elderly care services, and improve the elderly's sense of gain, happiness and satisfaction.

1.2 Concepts Related to Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services

1.2.1 Government Purchase of Pension Services

Government Procurement Services originated in western developed countries in the 1960s and has been developed for nearly 60 years. It refers to the fact that the government delivers services for social development and people's life to qualified social organizations by "purchasing" services, and pays the service fees after evaluating the quantity and quality of services provided by social organizations in accordance with pre-determined standards. ^[4]

Government purchase of elderly care services is a new model of government purchase of elderly care services, in which the elderly care services undertaken by the government are entrusted to social organizations for contract management and evaluation and cashing. The entrusting subject of government purchase of pension service is the government, and the entrusted person is pension institution and other social organizations. The object of purchase is pension service. The specific form is a contractual "purchase" behavior that pays all or part of the cost through government finance. Government purchase of elderly care services is a feasible way to improve the quality of public services. The types of pension service purchase include formal purchase, non-competitive purchase, competitive purchase, direct subsidy, and government subsidy.

1.2.2 Third-Party Performance Evaluation

The third-party performance evaluation refers to the evaluation carried out by the third-party organization that has no subordinate relationship or interest relationship with the government, also known as external evaluation, which is a professional organization evaluation independent of the government. ^[5] In terms of government purchase of elderly care services, third-party evaluation mainly refers to the evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services and its results by universities and professional evaluation institutions that have a good understanding of the elderly care service field and have been engaged in elderly care service research for a long time. The evaluation objects include institutional nursing homes subsidized by the government, enterprises and social organizations such as home-based nursing homes, and the

evaluation of the ability of the elderly, etc. In addition, it also involves the third-party evaluation of the actual effect of public financial funds used for special pension funds.

In the process of government purchase of elderly care services, third-party performance evaluation has its professional advantages and can scientifically quantify the indicators and participate in the whole process and all-around performance evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services. In order to improve the efficiency of evaluation, the government often hands over the pension subsidy to a third party when it sets the pension service payment standard. Third-party participation in the evaluation of the health status of older persons and the actual need for elderly care services.

In the field of pension service, service performance evaluation is extremely difficult. On the one hand, due to the complexity of pension service itself, although the evaluation of material pension service can achieve the quantification of indicators to a certain extent, However, mental endowment services are difficult to be quantified and quantitatively analyze. The expertise of the third party can give play to its advantages in index design and evaluation model construction.

1.3 Theoretical Basis of Third-Party Evaluation of Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services

1.3.1 Information Asymmetry Theory

In the process of government purchase of elderly care services, it mainly involves the government civil affairs department as the purchasing subject, the pension institutions as the undertaking subject, the pension service object as the income subject, and the third party as the evaluation subject. There is information asymmetry among the four types of subjects.^[6] The elderly service object has insufficient information and is in a vulnerable position. In order to ensure the quality and efficiency of the government's purchase of pension services, it is necessary to introduce a third-party evaluation mechanism to evaluate the performance of the purchase of pension services based on specialization and scale effect, so as to reduce the cost of civil affairs departments and pension service objects to obtain information related to pension services.

1.3.2 Principal-Agent Theory

In the process of government purchase of pension services, a principal-agent relationship is formed between the pension service object of the beneficiary and the government civil affairs department of the purchaser, and between the civil affairs department of the purchaser and the pension institution of the undertaking.^[6] As the three parties have different statuses and identities, the behavioral goals of the three parties may be inconsistent, resulting in the government's purchase of pension services cannot reach the target preset by the entrusting party. In order to ensure to undertake pension institution in accordance with the income the subject interests of endowment service object demand, purchase endowment is required for the main body of civil administration of government administrative services, the introduction of a third-party evaluation main body, through independent, professional and authoritative supervision, an effective checks and balances, provide needed pension services for the old-age service object.

1.3.3 360-Degree All-Round Performance Evaluation Theory

360-degree performance evaluation is the product of the combination of performance management and modern human resource management, including external customer evaluation, which effectively solves the lack of self-evaluation and makes the evaluation results more objective and fairer. The 360-degree performance evaluation of enterprises is also applicable to the performance evaluation of the government's purchase of elderly care services. Whether the purchase of pension services by the government meets the needs of the public, whether the use of financial funds is appropriate, and whether the self-performance evaluation of government departments is suspected of "dragging and singing". The 360-degree all-round performance evaluation provides theoretical support for the introduction of third-party evaluation in government purchase services. The starting point of 360-degree performance evaluation is to expand the scope of evaluation subjects and make the evaluation results more accurate and comprehensive.^[6]

2. Analysis on the Status Quo of Purchasing Elderly Care Services and Third-Party Performance Evaluation in Jiangsu Province, China

2.1 Analysis of Elderly Population

2.1.1 Analysis of the National Elderly Population

As shown in Table 1, in recent five years, the proportion of the elderly population aged 65 and above in China has been increasing, accounting for 13.5% in 2020, which has greatly exceeded the international standard of 7% for an aging society (the proportion of the population aged 60 and above is more than 10%, or the proportion of the population aged 65 and above is more than 7%), and has rapidly entered an aging society.

Table 1. Population Data of China from 2017 to 2020^[7]

Year	Total population Unit :(ten thousand)	Age 65 and above	
		Population	Proportion (%)
2017	138271	15003	10.8
2018	139008	15831	11.4
2019	140005	17603	12.6
2020	141178	19064	13.5

Table 2. Change Trend of Population Aging Scale and Proportion in China (2015-2060)^[8]

Year	Size of population aged 60 and above		%
	Total (100 million people)	Annual net increase (ten thousand)	
2015	2.21	958	16.1
2020	2.54	447	18.1
2025	3.04	1172	21.6
2030	3.65	1356	26.0
2035	4.12	669	29.8
2040	4.32	286	32.0
2045	4.48	249	34.0
2050	4.80	749	37.8
2055	4.84	267	39.8
2060	4.64	511	40.4

Figure 1. Line chart of proportion of elderly population over 60 years old in China (2015-2060)

The proportion of China's elderly population aged 60 and above keeps increasing, accounting for 18.10% in 2020, which has greatly exceeded the international standard of an aging society of 7% (over 10% of the population aged 60 or over 7% of the population aged 65 or over), and has rapidly entered an aging society. The aging of the population in China has four characteristics: large quantity, fast speed, big difference and heavy task.

Table 3 Changes of Registered Elderly Population in Jiangsu Province from 2018-2020^[9]

Age structure	End 2018	Compared with last year change	End 2019	Compared with last year change	End 2020	Compared with last year change
The registered population of Jiangsu province (A)	7835.72	30.1	7865.82	30.1	7841.22	30.1
Aged 60 and above (B)	1805.27	28.89	1834.16	28.89	1885.03	28.89
B/A proportion	23.04%	0.28%	23.32%	0.28%	24.04%	0.72%
Aged 65 and above (C)	1256.45	73.84	1330.29	73.84	1394.95	73.84
C/A proportion	16.03%	0.88%	16.91%	0.88%	17.79%	0.88%
Aged 80 and above (D)	270.96	9.08	280.04	9.08	288.56	9.08
D/A proportion	3.46%	0.10%	3.56%	0.10%	3.68%	0.12%

Figure 2. Analysis Chart of Population Proportion Trend of the Elderly in Jiangsu during 2018-2020

Compared with the size of the population aged 60 and above in China, the total population aged 60 and above in Jiangsu has reached 18.8503 million in 2020, accounting for 24.04% of the total population in Jiangsu and 6 percentage points higher than the national population. As can be seen from Figure 2, in general, among the registered elderly population in Jiangsu province, those over 60 years old increased from 23.04% in 2018 to 24.04% in 2020. Those aged 65 and above rose from 16.03% in 2018 to 17.79% in 2020. Those aged 80 or above increased from 3.46 percent in 2018 to 3.68 percent in 2020; The proportion is on the rise, not only the aging situation is getting worse, but also the aging problem is becoming increasingly serious. The aging elderly population will occupy more medical resources, Jiangsu pension pressure is increasing.

At present, Jiangsu province has formulated different policies for purchasing old-age care services for the elderly of different ages. Subsistence allowance over 60 years old and low income (subsistence allowance standard less than 2 times) lost alone elderly care, 60-79 years old dispersed support disabled half-disabled

elderly people, over 80 years old dispersed support disabled elderly people and subsistence care elderly people enjoy 75 yuan per month (3 hours per month) home care services. As long as 80 years old people apply in the community have the subsidy of respect for the elderly gold.

The issue of the elderly is the elderly over 80 years old to apply for the community, 80-89 years old can enjoy a monthly subsidy of 50 yuan, 90-99 years old can enjoy a monthly subsidy of 100 yuan, and the elderly over 100 years old can enjoy a monthly subsidy of 400 yuan.

2.2 The Current Situation of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

Jiangsu is a major economic province in China. The permanent resident population ranks fifth in China. Jiangsu's per capita GDP, comprehensive competitiveness, regional development, and livelihood index (DLI) rank first among all provinces in China, making Jiangsu the province with the highest level of comprehensive development in China. In Jiangsu province, the total demand for elderly care services is increasing rapidly, the service quality requirements are constantly improving, and the financial resources are limited, The contradiction between the traditional government supply mode and the increasing demand for the quantity and quality of pension service is becoming more and more prominent, Government purchase of pension service becomes a feasible way to improve the level of pension service.

2.2.1 Forms of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

According to the Government Procurement Law of the People's Republic of China, the current model of purchasing elderly care services in Jiangsu mainly includes the mode of bidding and the mode of "award instead of subsidy" for the special fund of elderly care construction.

(1) Bidding Mode

Bidding mode is a form of Jiangsu buy endowment service, the government directly online publish pension service projects according to the requirements of the elderly (general for the civil affairs bureau website). The eligible enterprises or social groups can be public bidding in accordance with the requirements of the project. The government finally sign the contract with the bid-winning enterprises or social organizations which conform to the conditions. The whole bidding process was open to the public, The government pays companies or social organizations according to the completion of service contracts agreed in advance.

(2) Reward in Place of Subsidy Mode

Replacing subsidies with awards" means subsidies to qualified pension institutions, home-based service centers, and other recipients in the form of special funds for pension construction by the government. The government will favor economically weak areas and rural areas when it designates pension service policies. The government subsidies to northern Jiangsu and economically weak areas are more than those to southern Jiangsu. For example, the provincial demonstration community home care service center is 150,000 yuan in economically weak areas and 100,000 yuan in other areas. New rural community home care service center (station) to meet the standards of the project, each subsidy of Southern Jiangsu 10,000 yuan, Jiangsu central 15,000-yuan, Northern Jiangsu 18,000 yuan. Public rural "elderly care home", the maximum subsidy of 150,000 yuan, other 100,000 yuan.

(3) Old-Age Care Beds Per 1,000 Elderly Population in Jiangsu

Table 4. Old-age beds per thousand elderly Population in Jiangsu Province^[10] unit: bed

Region	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Jiangsu	38.61	41.02	40.33	40.23	39.45	40.9

Growth of the total number of beds for the elderly in Jiangsu Province

Total number and growth rate of all kinds of old-age beds in Jiangsu Province from 2014 to 2020

Figure 3. Total number and growth rate of various old-age care beds in Jiangsu from 2014 to 2020

The total number of beds for the elderly is growing every year in Jiangsu, with 743,000 beds built by the end of 2020. The number of beds for the elderly per 1,000 elderly population in Jiangsu is basically stable at 40, showing a trend of slow fluctuation. Although the number of beds for the elderly is increasing every year in Jiangsu, the elderly population in Jiangsu is also on the rise. As a whole, the number of beds for the elderly per 1,000 elderly population in Jiangsu is relatively stable, and there is no rapid growth.

2.2.2 Analysis of Allocation of Special Funds for Provincial Pension Service Construction

Table 5. Allocation of Special Funds for Provincial Pension Construction^[11]

Unit: Ten thousand Yuan

Area	2018		2019		2020	
	Amounts	%	Amounts	%	Amounts	%
Nanjing	2794	4.81%	2617	4.25%	2609	4.24%
Wuxi	2428	4.18%	2485	4.03%	2585	4.20%
Xuzhou	7855	13.52%	9183	14.91%	9491	15.41%
Changzhou	1986	3.42%	1797	2.92%	1730	2.81%
Suzhou	3674	6.32%	3162	5.13%	3185	5.17%
Nantong	7806	13.44%	7029	11.41%	7263	11.79%
Lianyungang	4151	7.14%	4923	7.99%	4763	7.73%
Huaian	4591	7.90%	5112	8.30%	5044	8.19%
Yancheng	7265	12.50%	8574	13.92%	8462	13.74%
Yangzhou	4233	7.29%	4205	6.83%	3972	6.45%
Zhenjiang	1743	3.00%	1883	3.06%	1781	2.89%
Taizhou	5113	8.80%	4991	8.10%	4957	8.05%
Suqian	4461	7.68%	5639	9.15%	5758	9.35%
Total	58100	100%	61600	100%	61600	100%

As shown in Table 5, the allocation of special funds for provincial pension service construction in 13 cities of Jiangsu Province from 2018 to 2020 is sorted out. The analysis shows that while the number of the registered elderly population and the number of beds per thousand elderly people are increasing, the allocation of special funds for provincial pension construction is also increasing. In 2018, the provincial pension service construction special fund was 581 million yuan, and in 2019 and 2020 it was 616 million yuan. In 2020, considering the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic, the budget was not increased, but it was the same as that in 2019. The aging population has brought continuous pressure to Jiangsu's financial expenditure. Provincial financial funds tend to the less developed areas in northern Jiangsu when allocating

resources. The analysis of the provincial financial funds in southern Jiangsu is relatively small, which is due to the strong financial strength of the cities in southern Jiangsu and the guarantee of their own supporting pension funds. Of course, although the proportion of provincial pension construction special funds in Jiangsu cities is not completely consistent with the proportion of the registered elderly population in Jiangsu, generally speaking, it is generally consistent. It can be foreseen that Jiangsu will continue to promote the purchase of old-age services, and the investment of special funds for old-age construction will be further increased.

2.2.3 Main Achievements of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

(1) Construction of Community Elderly Care Facilities was Accelerated

The coverage rate of urban and rural community home care service centers in Jiangsu province has reached 100% and 96% respectively. By the end of 2020, a total of 2,374 nursing homes and 743,000 nursing beds have been built in the province. Among them, 534,700 beds for the elderly are run or operated by social forces, which means that the government buys elderly care services. There are 293,200 nursing beds for the combination of traditional Chinese medicine and health care. Jiangsu has promoted the socialization, branding and chain expansion of community elderly care services. It has built 18,200 community elderly care centers, 589-day care centers for the elderly in towns and townships, 8,094 assisted meals for the elderly in communities, and 33.58 million people have received home-based elderly care services. In 2020, the Jiangsu provincial pension service special fund will reach 616 million yuan.

(2) The System of Government Purchasing Elderly Care Services has been Gradually Improved

All municipalities have established a system of government purchasing elderly care services, and the documents of government purchasing elderly care services will be forwarded in the province. By the end of 2020, the number of people purchasing services in the province will account for 8% of the total number of elderly people. Urban areas have established a "trinity" system of government-purchased elderly care services, such as "home-based elderly care information call service, home-based elderly care door-to-door service and elderly care institution service.

(3) Further Progress was Made in Integrating Medical and Elderly care

The Jiangsu provincial government has formulated and issued the Notice on Improving Medical Services in Elderly Care Institutions in Jiangsu and The Implementation Opinions on Comprehensively Promoting the Integrated Development of Medical and Elderly Care in Jiangsu, which has initially established a policy system for the integrated development of medical and elderly care. Urban and rural grass-roots medical and health institutions have achieved good results in establishing health records and carrying out health management for the elderly. Vigorously supporting and developing the construction of nursing homes, so far the province has built a combination of medical care and nursing institutions of 293,200 beds. Jiangsu will promote the deep integration of medical and health resources with nursing homes, encourage health service institutions to provide resident services in nursing homes and implement the system of visiting nursing homes by medical institutions.

2.3 Analysis of Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

According to the Opinions on comprehensively Implementing Budget Performance Management issued by the CPC Central Committee and the State Council, the government should establish a comprehensive, whole-process and full-coverage budget performance management system for purchasing elderly care services, so as to achieve the performance goal of effective spending and accountability for ineffective spending. In this background, the performance evaluation of the third party for purchasing elderly care services in Jiangsu province is particularly important. Compared with foreign third-party performance evaluation, China's third-party performance evaluation develops slowly. At present, local governments in China are actively exploring the introduction of third-party performance evaluation in the process of

government purchase of elderly care services. Jiangsu, as a province with a large population, is no exception.

2.3.1 Third-Party Professional Evaluation of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu province

Municipal civil affairs departments entrust third-party professional evaluation institutions for the elderly, all those who apply to purchase elderly care services in Jiangsu Province, Third-party will carry out household surveys, capacity assessment, information registration and agency approval, and reduce the initial examination process in communities (villages). The elderly can complete the application approval work without leaving home, and enjoy government-purchased pension services according to the provisions. The third-party pension professional evaluation involves three parts:

(1) Evaluation in Advance of Purchasing Elderly Care Service -- Elderly People's Ability Evaluation

The capability assessment of the elderly is an important basis for the government to purchase home care services and live in nursing institutions. Through government procurement bidding, qualified third-party evaluation agencies with professional evaluation capabilities are determined. The third-party evaluation agency shall have at least 5 assessors, who shall have a medical or nursing education background, or have obtained social worker qualification certificate, or senior nursing worker qualification certificate, and have been specially trained to obtain assessor qualification certificate. A third-party professional evaluation agency will evaluate the capability of the elderly one by one, and evaluate whether they meet the semi-disability or disability of the elderly who purchase pension services. The third-party assessment is based on the Capability Assessment Standard for the Elderly (MZ/ T039-2013) issued by the Ministry of Civil Affairs. By the end of 2020, 33.58 million people who had benefited from government-purchased elderly care services had received home care services in Jiangsu Province. The standardization, informatization, and specialization of capacity assessment make capacity assessment more convenient, fast, and efficient, greatly ensure the objectivity and fairness of the assessment and enhance the credibility of the government.

(2) Evaluation of Nursing Home Service Quality

The evaluation was based on 115 guidelines for the inspection of nursing home service quality. To obtain corresponding service qualifications according to law by evaluating categories; Service personnel to meet service needs; Standardize service management; Requirements for facilities, equipment and articles; Create a safe and comfortable service environment; Providing basic living care services for the elderly on their own; Provide basic living care services for some disabled elderly people; Provision of basic life care services for disabled older persons; Provide room cleaning services; To provide safe and balanced meals; Health care services; Promoting health management of the elderly; Prevent nursing home infection; Assist the new elderly to adapt to the nursing home life; Provide psychological counseling, conflict mediation, crisis intervention and other services for the elderly; Carry out cultural entertainment activities suitable for the physical and mental characteristics of the elderly; Organize volunteers to serve the elderly, advocate the elderly to help each other, old age; Ensure fire safety; Ensure the safety of special equipment and properly deal with emergencies. Among them, 54 are basic standard indicators, and the rest are improvement indicators. The government gives pension institutions one-time construction subsidies according to their beds. Government subsidies for the operation of institutions must be classified according to the degree of disability of the elderly. The third-party assessment focuses on checking whether one person has one record, whether the number is right, and verifying the level of disability. Special government pension funds are provided to eligible elderly care institutions and home-based service centers in the form of awards in lieu of subsidies according to the subsidy standards that different regions enjoy. The government subsidies to northern Jiangsu and economically weak areas are more than those to southern Jiangsu. In addition, Subsidies to rural areas are also relatively high. For example, home care service centers in provincial demonstration communities will be subsidized 150,000 yuan in economically weak areas such as

northern Jiangsu, and 100,000 yuan in other areas. New rural community home care service center (station) to meet the standards of the project, each subsidy of Southern Jiangsu 10,000 yuan, Jiangsu central 15,000-yuan, Northern Jiangsu 18,000 yuan. Government-run rural "elderly care homes" can receive subsidies of up to 150,000-yuan, 50,000 yuan higher than other areas.

(3) Evaluation of Home Care Services.

The elderly's physical condition is assessed by a third party to determine whether they are eligible for home care services. There are 33.58 million visits to home care services purchased by the government, which meet the disability and semi-disability standards and enjoy six kinds of assistance, including assisted meals, assisted baths, assisted walking, assisted emergencies, and assisted medical services. According to the provincial document standards, semi-disabled elderly people can enjoy 300 yuan of home care services per month, and disabled elderly people can enjoy 400 yuan of home care services per month. The funds for on-site survey and evaluation of home-based elderly care are 60 yuan per person per time and 40 yuan per person per time for capacity evaluation of elderly people living in nursing institutions.

2.3.2 Analysis of Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

The document No.34 of the CPC Central Committee and The State Council in 2018, Opinions of the CPC Central Committee and The State Council on Comprehensively Implementing Budget Performance Management, clearly points out that "comprehensively implementing budget performance management" is a strategic deployment to comprehensively promote the modernization of national governance system and governance capacity, and third-party institutions are introduced to participate in budget performance management when necessary. In the same year the Ministry of Finance issued "the Ministry of Finance on promoting government purchasing service performance evaluation of the third party work guidance" (after CaiZong [2018] no. 42), 2019, Jiangsu provincial party committee, the provincial government issued on the implementation of the full implementation of the budget performance Jiangsu province government purchasing service performance evaluation system for the third party", Jiangsu actively pilot, In succession response, each city introduced the corresponding supporting policies.

2.3.2.1 Jiangsu Purchase Service Third-Party Performance Evaluation System

According to the Performance Evaluation Index System of Third-party Government Purchasing Services in Jiangsu Province released by the Jiangsu Provincial Department of Finance, the design principles of the index system for purchasing elderly care services in Jiangsu province are as follows: First, the principle of goal orientation. The performance evaluation should combine the individual and the whole goal and think about the problem with the whole concept. Second, the principle of the combination of generality and individuality. Third, the combination of qualitative and quantitative, qualitative indicators should not exceed 20% of the system quantity). Fourth, stability and prospective combination. Fifth, give consideration to performance and compliance.

Table 6. Basic Indicators of Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Government Purchase Services in Jiangsu Province ^[12]

Level 1 indicators	Level 2 indicators	Level 3 indicators
Invest capital	Funds to carry out	Capital availability ratio=(Actual funds in place/Plan to invest) *100%
		On-time rate= (Timely funding/Funds due) *100%
Process management	Business management	The soundness of the management system
		Effectiveness of system implementation
	Financial management	The soundness of the management system
		Fund use compliance
Output	Project output	Quantity index
		Quality index
Effect	Project benefits	Economic efficiency
		Social effect

Table 7. Optional Indexes of Performance Evaluation of Third-Party Government Purchase Services in Jiangsu Province ^[12]

Level 1 indicators	Level 2 indicators	Level 3 indicators
Input	Project approve	Standardization of project establishment
		The rationality of performance target
		Clear performance indicators
Process	Business management	Project quality control
	Financial management	Effectiveness of financial monitoring
Output	Project output	Completion Rate=[(planned completion time-actual finish time) /planned completion time]*100%
		Cost saving rate=[(planned cost-actual cost) /planned cost]*100%
Effect	Project benefits	Ecological benefits
		Sustainable impact
	satisfaction	Public satisfaction
		Customer satisfaction

At present, the reference frame of performance evaluation is roughly divided into basic indicators (see Table 6) and optional indicators (see Table 7). The third-party conducts evaluation based on basic indicators and optional indicators, including ① The implementation of policy formulation mainly evaluates the local supporting policies, plans, system construction, and implementation. ② Project fund management mainly evaluates financial fund investment, fund allocation progress, fund use, fund management system construction, and fund management work. ③ The completion of the project mainly evaluates the progress and quality of the completion of the fund assignment task indicators. In recent years, each city in Jiangsu province has been activated based on the "Jiangsu Provincial Government Purchase Service third-party Performance Evaluation Index System" pilot, each city will choose one or two key pension projects for key evaluation every year.

Table 8. Financial Management Indicators and Scores Involved in Third-Party Performance Evaluation^[12] Units: Points

Financial Management		15
Financial Management System	Establish payment management system, implement payment approval process and implement it	1
	The elderly deposit management system and implementation	2
	Have a donation fund management system and use the donated funds in accordance with the wishes of the donor and relevant regulations	1
	Have fixed assets and current assets management system and implement it	1
	Have annual financial audit and audit report	2
	Have an accounting file management system and implement it	2
	Government subsidy funds separate accounts, clear accounts (Note: If there is no government subsidy, it can be automatically scored)	1
	Have a budget and cost management system and implement it	1
	There is a budget and cost management system and it shall be implemented. There is a price management system and it shall be implemented. Any change in the service price charged to the elderly shall be informed to the elderly in advance and no compulsory fees shall be charged	1
Financial Personnel Management Requirements	Accounting personnel hold accounting qualification certificate	1
	Financial personnel are skilled in using computerized accounting equipment	1
	The person in charge of the financial department does not concurrently hold the position of the buyer; The person who fills in the bill and receipt does not concurrently serve as an auditor; the Cashier and bookkeeping personnel are separated, not concurrent with each other.	1

In addition, third-party performance evaluation institutions will also refer to the Implementation Guide of National Standards for Grading and Evaluation of Pension Institutions (Trial) to grade the pension services. In terms of financial management indicators, as shown in Table 8, a total of 15 points have been set (out of a full score of 120 points). It is divided into the financial management system (full score 12) and financial management personnel requirements (full score 3). Pay special attention to whether there is a financial audit and audit report and accounting file system and implementation.

2.3.2.2 Status Quo of Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

(1) Status Analysis

In the southern Jiangsu region, the analysis of the performance evaluation of the government's purchase of pension services by third-party institutions entrusted by Nanjing, Wuxi, Changzhou, Zhenjiang, and Suzhou during 2018-2020 shows that the five cities in southern Jiangsu carry out third-party performance evaluation of 1-5 key pension projects on the basis of self-evaluation every year. In 2018, Nanjing Civil Affairs Bureau entrusted a third party to carry out a key performance evaluation of 5 pension projects, and the winning amount reached 783,000 yuan. In 2019, Nanjing Civil Affairs Bureau entrusted a third party to carry out a key performance evaluation of 3 pension projects, and the winning amount reached 640,000 yuan. In 2020, Nanjing commissioned a third party to carry out a key performance evaluation for four pension projects, and the winning amount reached 660,000 yuan. By far the highest in southern Jiangsu is Nanjing.

In the northern Jiangsu region, Xuzhou, Lianyungang, Yancheng, Suqian, and Huai 'an are mainly self-evaluated, while Xuzhou, Yancheng, and Suqian are relatively positive in third-party performance evaluation. It can be seen on the public resource trading platform of Xuzhou that Xuzhou entrusted Xuzhou Zhongdixin Accounting Firm Co., Ltd. and Xuzhou Schindler Accounting Firm Co., Ltd. to conduct third-party performance evaluation, with an annual cost of nearly 200,000 yuan.

In central Jiangsu province, Yangzhou and Nantong, self-evaluation is the main factor. In 2018, Taizhou commissioned a third party to carry out a key evaluation of a pension project, and the winning amount was 120,000 yuan. In 2019 and 2020, another pension project entrusted a third party to carry out the key evaluation, and the winning amount was 90,000 yuan. Compared with Yangzhou and Nantong, third-party institutions are more active in participating in the performance evaluation of purchasing elderly care services in Taizhou, a city in central Jiangsu Province. Nantong's allocation of provincial pension funds ranked second, but the third-party institutions' participation in performance evaluation did not keep pace with the pace of fund matching.

(2) Reason Analysis

On the one hand, the government to buy endowment service performance evaluation of the third party is still in active pilot, the current public bidding of the government to buy endowment service performance evaluation of the third party is not very common, building special funds in pension is given priority to with the evaluation, on the basis of each city, each year will select several important pension programs of key evaluation, the evaluation results will be on the platform of the public budget.

At present, the main body of third-party evaluation is an accounting firm and research institution. Compared with the special fund of Jiangsu provincial pension construction, the fund used for third-party performance evaluation is very small. In addition, although some cities in Jiangsu have adopted third-party performance evaluation, no third-party performance evaluation fund has been included in the budget. There is also a need to scrape together funds for third-party performance evaluation, so the third-party performance evaluation is not very positive in Central Jiangsu compared with southern Jiangsu.

(3) Analysis of effects

Jiangsu province has been constantly exploring and trying to purchase the third-party performance evaluation of elderly care services and has achieved good results.

① Improved the efficiency of the use of special government funds for the elderly. The third-party performance evaluation institutions conduct performance evaluation on the financial special pension funds and monitor the use of the financial special pension funds from the four aspects of input, output, process, and effect, which can effectively improve the use efficiency of the special pension funds and promote economic development and reasonable allocation of resources.

With the continuous advancement of third-party performance evaluation mechanisms, more and more attention will be paid to the difference between the budget expenditure and actual expenditure of government pension funds, and more and more attention will be paid to the use of funds used for government purchase, and important performance evaluation indicators will be included. This will make pension recipients feel more pressure, and constantly optimize the use of funds allocated by the government.

② Helps the government to find problems. Third-party performance evaluation agencies help the government find problems in the evaluation process, namely in budget management: the budget preparation is not rigorous and needs to be standardized; Total budget control of key projects, lack of specific project budget analysis, part of the project budget arrangement there is certain randomness. In terms of

performance management: the department has not yet established a complete and standardized overall performance evaluation management mechanism.

③ Accelerate the development of community elderly care services. The participation of the third-party performance evaluation in the evaluation of the government's purchase of pension services can effectively supervise the use of funds by the pension undertaking subject, as well as the service level provided by the pension undertaking subject, and accelerate the service quality construction of the pension undertaking subject in China.

④ The standardized development of third-party performance evaluation for government purchase of elderly care services has been promoted. Jiangsu province is the earlier one of which is based on medical raise pension pilot provinces and to promote the institution endowment and community endowment and home support through a variety of ways, a third party in the performance evaluation of government purchase endowment service practice, can constantly find the problems from the reality of external level and promoting the development of purchase endowment service standardization.

⑤ Improving the quality of purchasing elderly care services. The third-party performance evaluation of the government's purchase of pension service plays an effective external supervision role on the undertaking subject, which can make the undertaking subject aware of the shortcomings of the current services provided so as to continuously improve the quality and level of their own pension service.

⑥ An individuals' sense of happiness and gain has improved. The introduction of a third-party performance evaluation mechanism makes the public no longer have a sense of worry about the services provided by pension recipients. The sons and daughters of the elderly also have more trust in the services provided by the undertaker and are willing to let their parents live in the house. To some extent, this alleviates the conflict between children who want to take care of the elderly but have no time and energy and improves people's sense of happiness and gain in life.

3. Constructs the Performance Evaluation Mechanism of the Third Party for Purchasing Elderly Care Service in Jiangsu Province

To construct the third-party evaluation mechanism, it is necessary to make the mechanism play its due role in the government's purchase of old-age services, prevent the administrative risk transfer or avoidance behavior, and make the mechanism play a substantial role to prevent formalism.

3.1 Principles for the Construction of Third-Party Performance Evaluation Mechanism for Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services^[13]

3.1.1 People's Livelihood Oriented

In the construction of a third-party evaluation mechanism for government purchase of elderly care services, the government should uphold the principal role of the elderly, adhere to the concept of people-oriented and evaluation for the people, ensure and improve people's livelihood and the quality of elderly care services, expand channels for public participation, conduct demand analysis and satisfaction surveys on public elderly care services, and reflect the most authentic voice of the underclass. the third-party professional evaluation should serve to better meet the growing needs of the people in elderly care services.

3.1.2 Collaborative Governance

Pension service is a public demand, is the need of the whole society, not only the government but also the whole society. The modernization of national governance requires the government to gradually turn to governance in the process of providing old-age services. Through effective interaction between the government and the public, cooperation and consultation relationships can be established and mutual recognition in old-age services can be achieved in order to realize the governance of public old-age services. In the construction of a third-party evaluation mechanism for government purchase of elderly care

services, Social forces should be recognized and encouraged to participate in public pension service, pay attention to the diversification of public pension service supply subjects, take people's satisfaction as the main evaluation index, pay attention to reflect the real concerns of beneficiaries of public pension service, through the formation of an effective collaborative governance system, to solve the problems of insufficient supply, low efficiency, low quality and unbalanced structure of public pension service, so as to effectively meet the demand for pension service.

3.1.3 Focus on Performance

Performance management is an effective mode and means for the government to carry out pension service governance, and performance evaluation is one of the main contents of performance management. Budget performance management is an important part of government public service governance, and fiscal expenditure performance evaluation is the core of budget performance management. The government's purchase of pension services is finally reflected in the fiscal budget expenditure, and performance evaluation is indispensable. Therefore, the third-party evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services is directly aimed at emphasizing the result-oriented budget expenditure, paying attention to the responsibility and efficiency of expenditure, improving budget expenditure management, optimizing the allocation of financial resources, and improving the quality of elderly care services.

In the process of building a third-party evaluation mechanism for government purchase of elderly care services, The concept of performance should be integrated into the whole process of evaluation so as to pay more attention to the output and results of pension service brought by financial investment.

3.2 Key Points of Third-Party Evaluation Mechanism Construction for Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services^[13]

In the construction of a third-party evaluation mechanism. We should avoid the one-sided judgment of "substitution theory", "uniqueness theory", "specialty theory" and "independence theory", and correct the wrong practice of substituting third-party evaluation for self-evaluation and re-evaluation carried out by departments such as finance and purchasing subject or undertaking subject. The third-party evaluation should be an integral part of the evaluation system for government purchase of elderly care services, so as to share evaluation information and evaluation results with other evaluations. At the same time, it must be clear that the third-party independent evaluate the endowment service bought by the government, it is not meaning that the involved main body participation doesn't need to take part in the service, while the third party evaluation should be open, actively absorb the purchase of the subject, object of service and other related parties to participate in, especially in the process of the specific evaluation we should open endowment service benefit object feedback channel, Take their satisfaction as a major evaluation index to enhance the sense of acquisition of service objects. In order to avoid the problem of "amateurs evaluating professionals", especially third-party performance evaluation, internal and external evaluation should be combined to construct a multi-subject collaborative participation pattern, and the role of third-party evaluation should not be overly biased.

3.2.1 Build Boundary Framework

We should clarify the scope of the third-party evaluation mechanism and "what to evaluate". The third-party evaluation mechanism should play a role in the whole process before, during, and after the purchase of pension services by the government. The pension objects should be professionally evaluated in advance and then evaluated afterward, which can be divided into three levels:

① At the level of pension service management, the third-party evaluation mechanism plays a role in the whole process of pension service project setting and decision-making, government purchase and undertaking of the main body to provide, and benefit of the main body to accept and enjoy.

- ② Budget management level, the third-party evaluation mechanism plays a role in the whole process of budget preparation, budget implementation, and final accounts for the government's purchase of elderly care services.
- ③ Performance management level, the third-party evaluation mechanism should play a role in the whole process of setting and decomposition of performance objectives, implementation, and promotion, analysis, evaluation, and application of results.

3.2.2 Building a Support system

Forming the element conditions of the third-party evaluation mechanism and clarifying "how to evaluate"

- ① Strengthen institutional support. The construction of a third-party evaluation system should be strengthened with documents and standards to provide a solid institutional foundation and strong institutional guarantee for the smooth development of third-party evaluation, and the functions, procedures, tasks, and main contents of third-party evaluation should be clarified so that there are laws and regulations for third-party evaluation to follow. To strengthen the construction of the professional standards for third-party evaluation, clarify the professional standards of relevant institutions and personnel in third-party evaluation, and standardize the operating procedures.
- ② Strengthen standard support. Relying on the basic old-age service standards already established by the state, accelerate the establishment of the corresponding classification, efficient and user-friendly third-party evaluation standards and realize dynamic adjustment, so as to provide a clear scale to measure the achievement of the performance target of the government in purchasing old-age services.
- ③ Strengthen indicator support. In carrying out a third-party evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services, referring to the Common Index System Framework of Budget Performance Evaluation issued by the Ministry of Finance, common indexes should be set according to the actual situation of government purchase of public services and constantly improved according to the characteristics of third-party evaluation and the needs of actual work. It is also necessary to design specific personality evaluation indexes according to the characteristics of pension service projects. At the same time, various evaluation indicators should be given scientific and reasonable weight, evaluation criteria should be specified and refined, and any applicable third-party evaluation indicator system should be formed.

3.2.3 Build Dynamic Mechanism^[13]

The third-party evaluation mechanism should effectively consider the interests of all parties and clarify the "why evaluation". In the construction of a third-party evaluation mechanism for government purchase of elderly care services, it is necessary to emphasize scientific cost-effectiveness. However, it is absolutely not necessary to establish a simple, one-sided, and short-sighted concept of purchasing elderly care services for the purpose of reducing expenditure. Instead, it should take the principle of value for money and establish a benefit-driven mode oriented by service performance. For government purchases of public services to undertake the main body, third party evaluation is not merely to lower the price of the government purchasing service for the purpose, It is to assess whether the elderly care they actually provide achieves the goal of value for money. The purchase consideration payable to the Government shall not be discounted so long as the evaluation meets preset performance objectives. And the corresponding pre-set performance payment, forming a positive incentive mechanism, so that the government, pension service providers, the people win.

For third-party evaluation agencies, the government's purchase of evaluation services is not simply the lower the better, but should also be measured by the value for money standard. As long as third-party evaluation plays a positive role in improving the quality and efficiency of government-purchased elderly care services, it should be worthwhile for the government to pay the corresponding evaluation service fees. The selection

of third-party evaluation agencies should not be based on the service price, but should be guided by the quality of evaluation services, so that high-quality third-party evaluation agencies have both market, reputation and more profits. Only in this way can the standardized development of third-party evaluation industry have a dynamic mechanism.

3.2.4 Build Quality System

The third-party evaluation mechanism should effectively improve the quality and clarify "what kind of evaluation to provide". Establishing and maintaining the evaluation quality control system is not only an effective means to ensure the quality of third-party evaluation, but also a necessary condition for third-party evaluation institutions to expand their market development and growth, as well as one of the legal responsibilities of third-party evaluation institutions. Third-party evaluation institutions should constantly improve the quality of practitioners, scientifically set up review links, organically combine the hierarchical review of evaluation projects with the quality control review of evaluation institutions, and effectively improve the quality of third-party evaluation. At the same time, relevant government departments should establish a random inspection mechanism for the evaluation quality of third-party evaluation institutions to ensure the quality of evaluation work.

3.2.5 Building an Application Mechanism

The third-party evaluation mechanism should play an effective role and clarify "what is the use of evaluation". The third-party evaluation mechanism for government purchase of elderly care services should focus on the full and effective use of the evaluation results, timely feedback of the third-party evaluation results to the purchasers and receivers of elderly care services, urge them to rectify the problems found in the evaluation, and promote the improvement of the supply level of elderly care services. We will link third-party evaluation results with government pension subsidies, and improve the incentive and restraint mechanism for recipients. A mechanism will be established to combine the third-party evaluation results with the government's budget arrangement for purchasing elderly care services. If the evaluation results are not good, subsidies will be reduced or cancelled in principle. If the performance evaluation results are good, government subsidies will be prioritized.

4.Improve the Third Party Performance Evaluation Measures and Suggestions for Purchasing Elderly Care Services in Jiangsu Province

4.1 For Government Purchasers

4.1.1 Establish a Long-Term Mechanism for Third-Party Performance Evaluation

The inefficient use of some special funds for the elderly is not entirely a problem of project implementation, but defects in policy formulation and fund structure arrangement, and problems at this stage are often directional and fundamental. Therefore, the performance of special pension construction funds must start from the source, establish a third-party performance evaluation mechanism for major policies and projects in advance, and promote performance management to move forward. For major new policies and projects, prior performance evaluation should be carried out at the time of project approval. To summarize experience and establish a long-term mechanism of third-party performance evaluation, further prevent the occurrence of "head-beating decision", which is also a technical reserve for scientific implementation of performance evaluation in the future.

4.1.2 Scientifically Organize Third-Party Performance Evaluation

The third-party performance evaluation of pension service purchase is the core of pension budget fund performance management, and the relationship between quantity and quality should be handled well. Firstly, we should implement full coverage of pension fund performance self-evaluation to solve the problem of quantity. On this basis, civil affairs departments through the organization of re-evaluation, with the help of third-party institutions to carry out spot check and review of important data, to check the work of

self-evaluation, and at the same time require third-party evaluation results to the public, to promote the departments to improve the quality of self-evaluation work. Secondly, we should improve the precision and quality of the key evaluation of pension special construction funds and solve the qualitative problems.

4.1.3 Establish a Trinity Policy of "Home, Community and Institution" for Purchasing Elderly Care Services

Jiangsu should actively prepare for the aging of population. From the change trend of registered elderly population in the past three years, The elderly population in Jiangsu has increased from 18,052,700 in 2018, accounting for 23.04% of Jiangsu's total population of 78.357,200, to 18,341,700 in 2019, accounting for 23.35% of Jiangsu's total population of 78.554,100, and then to 18,853,300 in 2020. Accounting for 24.04% of Jiangsu's total population of 78.3999 million, The provincial pension construction special fund is 581 million yuan in 2018, and 616 million yuan in 2019 and 2020, with a growth rate of 6% or zero growth. When we formulate pension policies, we still need to focus on home-based care. After all, the health of the elderly is better than before, their economic income is higher, and their sense of well-being is higher at home and in the familiar areas around them. We will expand community-based elderly care, mainly in the form of home-based care centers and day care centers and solve the financial problems and long-term management problems involved in expanding the scope of government purchase of elderly care services; Government funds are limited, it is unrealistic to rely on the government for pension services. Currently, government purchases of elderly care services only involve people over the age of 60. In the financial permit we should also take care of the permanent resident elderly population in Jiangsu. In order to maximize the use efficiency of pension funds under the condition of limited funds, Necessary from the perspective of the whole process to invite a third party professional pension appraisal institutions, through its long-term in-depth research and pension professional knowledge, for the elderly community endowment service requirements of different types, the degree of urgency, the sequence of scientific research, rigorous sorting and distribution, third party can support the government for set up the trinity endowment service policy.

4.1.4 Establish a Rating and Training Mechanism for Pension Recipients

State-owned and private providers of old-age care will be evaluated and dynamically adjusted, and the same level will enjoy the same treatment, so that the quality of old-age care services will be linked to the government's purchase of old-age subsidies. To implement regular training system for nursing home institutions, especially the introduction of new policies, in order to better implement the policy documents, it is necessary to conduct centralized training for nursing homes to learn and understand the spirit of the documents. Especially small-scale pension institutions, poor management, lack of books, inadequate rectification. We should realize the real sense of the elderly service quality linked to the government to buy pension subsidies and give play to the incentive mechanism, mobilize the enthusiasm of people to serve the elderly.

4.1.5 Improve the Transparency of Information on Government Purchase of Elderly Care Services

We should provide work guarantee system for third party performance evaluation and remove information barriers. Authentic and complete information is the premise to guarantee the effect of third-party evaluation on government purchase of elderly care services. In accordance with the Regulations of the People's Republic of China on The Disclosure of Government Information and the relevant provisions on government purchase of public Services, government departments should broaden the channels for disclosure, and timely publish real information on the government information platform such as the standards, requirements, budget and fund arrangements, purchasers and undertakers of elderly care services and actively accept the public's evaluation, and guarantee the public's right to know, to participate, to express and to supervise.^[14] We should build detailed rules or methods in the process of purchasing elderly care services and set up and regulate information release standard format, process and channel scientifically, and establish the system of

information disclosure and reply and correction, and achieve benign communication between the multi-subjects of pension services, mutual understanding and support.

4.1.6 Enhance the Public's Understanding of Third-Party Performance Evaluation Institutions

The government should use news media and other media to enhance the public's awareness and understanding of third-party performance evaluation, so that the public can understand the significance of the existence of third-party performance evaluation, and can actively participate in it. Government can provide a channel for the public to express their own views and suggestions, and put the reasonable and desirable part into practical application.^[15]

4.1.7 Strengthen the Government's Supervision and Management of Third-Party Performance Evaluation of Pension Service Purchase.

① Strengthen the bidding and supervision of the third party, improve the third-party selection system, and ensure the independence of the third-party evaluation.^[16]

② Strengthen business training and guidance to carry out work. The government continuously strengthens the training of the third party, expands the third-party evaluation team, and improves the performance evaluation level.

③ Calculate the workload and determine the cost standard. "Service" needs to be "purchased", so it should be paid for. Expenditure of performance evaluation funds should also be based on performance.

④ In the Law on the Protection of The Rights and Interests of the Elderly and detailed rules of relevant policies, the legal status of third-party evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services has been established. The reform of the legal system for the management of third-party evaluation subjects will be promoted to ensure that third-party evaluation can be carried out smoothly in the early, middle and late stages of purchasing elderly care services according to actual conditions.

⑤ Relying on the legal person unit information database of pension service institutions and third-party evaluation institutions, the organization registration management information is improved, and the business records, credit records and social responses of third-party subjects are recorded and retained, so as to facilitate the inquiry and supervision of stakeholders.

⑥ We should strengthen supervision over third-party evaluation institutions during and after the event, and establish a mechanism for accepting and rewarding complaints and reports on violations of laws and regulations by third-party evaluation institutions. The public is encouraged to supervise third-party evaluation agencies.

4.2 Pension Undertaking Entity

4.2.1 Strengthen Business Training

A training mechanism has been established to improve the quality of services for elderly care recipients. Nursing home nurses should not only hold the certificate, but also regular rating, reward the diligent and punish the lazy. Elderly care recipients should establish skills training mechanisms and constantly improve service levels.

4.2.2 The Evaluation Results of Third-Party Evaluation Shall Be Included in the Assessment of Work Objectives of Pension Undertaking Entity.

It is necessary to establish and improve the information disclosure mechanism of pension service entity, imitate the information disclosure mechanism of charitable organizations or listed companies, standardize the information disclosure system of pension service undertaking entity, especially standardize the operation and format of information disclosure of pension undertaking entity, and actively cooperate with third-party evaluation. The information of pension entity and personnel will be released to the government and the public through a third-party evaluation platform for social supervision.

4.3 Third-Party Evaluation Entity

4.3.1. Establish and Improve the Reputation Incentive System for Third-Party Evaluation of Pension Services

Improve the internal governance of the third party, strengthen brand building, develop talent team, expand social influence, and constantly improve the ability of evaluation service, so as to provide higher quality evaluation service.

4.3.2 Strengthen the Third Party's Participation in the Government's Purchase of Old-Age Services Before and After the Service

Third-party evaluation institutions should strengthen their participation in the whole process of the purchased elderly service activities, strengthen the ability assessment of the elderly in advance, and strengthen the evaluation of the efficiency of the use of financial funds afterwards. The two should cooperate to improve the efficiency of participation.

4.3.3. Strengthen and Standardize the Management of Third-Party Evaluation Process

The third party shall establish and improve the performance evaluation information fidelity system in accordance with scientific and standardized performance evaluation procedures. The important feature of elderly care products is that production and supply are closely related or the same process, so it is necessary to strengthen the pre-evaluation of the service process, rather than focusing only on the evaluation of service results. It is difficult to collect the data of pension service process, which requires whole-process tracking. Third-party professional evaluation entity should participate in the whole process and all-round performance management mechanism of purchasing elderly care services. At the same time, an evaluation appeal system should be established to give the evaluated pension service institutions and pension service objects the right and opportunity to appeal and communicate with the evaluation results, and a scientific and reasonable appeal procedure should be designed. Ensure that third-party evaluation is legalized and democratized. This should be considered when we formulate pension policies.

4.3.4 Strengthen the Evaluation of Satisfaction Effect of Pension Service

The satisfaction index of elderly care service demand side is the most important index of effect evaluation. In view of the weak position of the elderly group in demand expression and interest protection, it is necessary to scientifically quantify the index system and optimize the evaluation of the effect of the elderly service.

5. Conclusion

The third-party evaluation has now become the proper meaning of the performance evaluation of the government purchasing the elderly service. In order to adapt to the needs of the new situation and new tasks, it is necessary to correctly understand and reasonably position third-party evaluation, and then effectively promote the application of third-party evaluation in a way suitable for the third party in Jiangsu to participate in the evaluation of elderly care services. Third-party evaluation of government purchase of elderly care services should be carried out throughout the whole process. Evaluate and analyse the feasibility of purchasing pension project plan before making it. During and after the implementation of the project, control the implementation of the purchase of old-age care services. We should strengthen the construction of laws, regulations and systems, improve the construction of third-party evaluation subjects, mobilize social forces for the elderly, and innovate evaluation methods and results application. With effective supervision as the guarantee, promote the institutionalization, industrialization and standardized development of third-party evaluation in Jiangsu province, to avoid abuse and blind promotion, establish a long-term mechanism for performance evaluation of third-party participation in purchasing elderly care services. We will allocate special funds for old-age care construction in a more scientific and rational way, and make good

use of and management of government funds drawn from the people so that the people can more equitably enjoy the fruits of reform.

Reference:

- i. Ministry of Finance, PRC , *Guidance on Promoting third-party performance Evaluation of Government Purchase Services*, Caizong [2018] No.42 On July 30, 2018
- ii. The General Office of the State Council of PRC , *the Opinions on Promoting the Development of Elderly Care Services*,No. 5,On March 29, 2019
- iii. The People's Government of Jiangsu Province,PRC , *Implementation Opinions on Further Promoting the High-quality Development of Elderly Care Services" su Zhengfa* (2019) No. 85.,December 23, 2019
- iv. Zhang Xiaohong, Wang Xiang, "Discussion on the Applicability of third-party Evaluation for Government Purchase of Public Services and Sustainable Construction", *Fiscal Supervision*, 2017, 22
- v. Zhang Zhenchuan, ZHANG Yueming, Li Hongru. *Research on third-party evaluation mechanism of fiscal expenditure performance -- Taking Hebei Province as an example [J]. Fiscal Supervision*,2017(01):55-57.
- vi. Zhong W F.A case study of guangdong Civil Affairs Department government purchasing home care outsourcing service [D]. *University of Electronic Science and Technology of China*,2013.
- vii. National Bureau of Statistics of PRC,*Population data in China Statistical Yearbook 2020*
- viii. Du Peng, Li Long. *Long-term Trend Prediction of Population aging in China in the New Era [J]. Journal of Renmin University of China*, 2021,35(01):96-109.
- ix. Government of Jiangsu Province, PRC, *Report on the Development of Undertakings for the Aged in Jiangsu Province* (2020)
- x. National Bureau of Statistics of PRC,*Yearbook of Chinese Social Statistics*(2020)
- xi. The People's Government of Jiangsu Province,PRC , *Notice on Allocating Special Funds for Provincial Social Old-age Service System Construction Subsidy issued by Su Caihe*(2020).
- xii. Jiangsu Provincial Department of Finance ,PRC , *Performance Evaluation Index System of Third Party Government Purchase Service in Jiangsu Province*(2020) .
- xiii. Jin Yaohan, "Thinking on the Function positioning and Mechanism Construction of third-party Evaluation for Government Purchase of Public Services" *Fiscal Supervision* 2018
- xiv. Wen Laicheng, Chen Xiaolin, "Difficulties and Policy Suggestions for Third-party Evaluation of Government Purchase of Public Services", *Fiscal Supervision*, 2017, 22
- xv. Sun Ling. *Research on third-party Evaluation System for Government Purchase of Public Services [D]. Hunan University*,2017.
- xvi. Zeng Jimao. *Does the Qualification access Mechanism of third-party institutions in Government Performance Evaluation Work? -- A case study of performance evaluation of Shanghai Government's purchase of social organization services [J]. Public Governance Review*,2018(02):79-88.